

MAIN STYLES AND DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF THE PIANO IN JAZZ PERFORMANCE IN THE 20TH CENTURY

Zikriyayev Mardon Maxamatjon o'g'li

Under the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

2nd year master's student of the Art Institute named after Botir Zakirov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7347153>

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of the piano in the musical culture of the 20th century, i.e., the performance of the jazz genre, and the trends in the development of performance styles.

Key words: Jazz, music culture, instrument performance, piano, Louis Armstrong, E. V. Lubyana, S. V. Davydov, tendency.

The piano is an important part of the history of the jazz music genre. This type of musical performance is versatile and can be seen in the work of musicians from all over the world. Performers who choose the piano have inherited the richest traditions, they develop them or fill them with innovations. Today, absolutely everything can be heard on the jazz piano scene, from ragtime, its original version and arranged in modern traditions, to avant-garde compositions with piano "preparation" during performance. Pianists mix academic and jazz traditions, using all styles and techniques. The piano repertoire is very large and includes both jazz classics and modern compositions. Many pianists create compositions that re-examine the heritage of jazz, imbuing them with a "modern" look.

The diversity of styles and trends, styles and forms in piano jazz music has created the need to understand this phenomenon. This explains the emergence of new research on the history, theory and problems of jazz pianism. Thus, the works of E.V. Lubyana "Piano in jazz throughout the 20th-21st centuries: origin, trends, originality" and B.G. Gnilov "Jazz pianism and piano art" show all aspects of this performance art, rib comes out, analyzes styles, reveals all "mechanisms" of interaction between performance methods and formats, piano jazz and different cultural layers - academic, ethnic and pop. S.V. Davydov in the article "Pianistic texture complexes as a source and means of artistic interpretation in jazz" focuses on improvisation, artistic interpretation and the role of texture in this process, composition, performance and improvisation interdependence. B. Stetsyuk's article "Modern piano jazz: typical stylistics and individual representations" examines the interaction of piano jazz with academic music, mainly on the example of Ukrainian pianist V. Neselovsky's work. In the article "Jazz piano performance in the 30-40s of the 20th century", P. K. Kornev presents a detailed classification of piano playing styles and formats in the first half of the 20th century. F.S.Shak's article "Stylistic

and performance aspects of piano jazz" is distinguished by a critical attitude: in the author's opinion, any interaction of jazz with other musical systems kills the nature of jazz and serves only to entertain a bored intellectual audience. Thus, it can be said that most of the theoretical work on piano jazz is based on the analysis of jazz styles and directions, the study of creative styles and improvisation methods of pianists, as well as the consideration of the "dialogue" of jazz pianism with various musical genres.

This article should complement a number of modern studies. It focuses on the study of piano jazz in the 20th century - that is, at the time when all styles, styles and techniques were formed, and the ways in which piano jazz and other musical traditions interacted.

The following tasks were set to achieve the expected results:

- 1) trace the history of the development of piano jazz in the 20th century;
- 2) To identify and classify the styles, creative styles and development trends of piano jazz formed during the 20th century.

The article uses methods of stylistic and holistic analysis. The work's practical value is seen in the summation of experience resulting from more than a century of development of the piano jazz tradition. Understanding these processes is essential to understanding the art of jazz piano.

Instrumental jazz performance is by nature a continuous process of overcoming stereotypes. Musicians developed an improvisational mindset, developed new ways of creating music on their own, broke the historically defined and established boundaries of the ranges of musical instruments, invented new ways of producing sound, changed timbre color and increased speed due to the use of mutes. A bright sign of jazz was the peculiarity of accepting performers "not of their own workshop" as a standard.

Ragtime is considered the starting point of piano jazz. Pieces in this style are not like jazz: they do not swing, there are no improvisational solos. Nevertheless, they had the syncopation adopted by early jazz orchestras. Ragtime, popular in the United States and Europe at the beginning of the twentieth century, became the basis for the Harlem piano style (Harlem was the center of piano jazz in the 1920s). But before that, instrumental blues, including piano, appeared in New Orleans. It was these very first pianists who learned to achieve the blue note effect by playing late at night in drinking establishments. We are talking about the III, V and VII degrees of the mode, which are usually designated as lowered in music literature, but are performed as microtones, that is, something in between, for example, III natural and III reduced. Vocalists, singers, guitarists freely reached this microtone. However,

black pianists quickly adapted to playing blues notes by switching from black keys to white keys.

Classical jazz in piano music is represented by Harlem piano and boogie-woogie styles. At the heart of stride piano, like ragtime, is the step technique (stride - step). The right hand part was deft and complex, based on the clear ground stroke of the left hand, and consisted of melodic lines, flowing passages and fioraturas. Boogie-woogie - piano blues played in the evening in entertainment establishments (this music is intended for dancing). And if the piano was played by professional pianists, then boogie-woogie could be played by amateurs. Of the classical jazz pianists, such musicians as W. L. Smith, D. P. Johnson, T. "F" should be noted. Waller, D. "R". Morton, P. Johnson, et al.

Piano jazz before the Bebop era (1940s) was a homophonic-harmonic fact-ru, that is, such a presentation of musical material in which the melody dominates and the accompaniment is in secondary "roles": it accompanies the melody ladi . However, in the first half of the 20th century, pianists appeared who deviated from this standard. The first of them was E. Hines (1903-1983). Constant accompaniment was not always present in his playing: often the melodic line "flows" from the right hand to the left and vice versa. More precisely, these were rapid "flows of sound" and, in general, his playing "is full of interrhythms, it is persistent, variable and bold".

Among the pianists of the swing era (M. Powell, D. Sullivan, T. Wilson, D. Stacey, M. Ash, etc.), it is worth mentioning two group leaders who mainly continued the traditions established earlier. We are talking about D. Ellington and K. Besi. These musicians led big bands and were pianists in their ensembles. D. Ellington (1899-1974) entered the history of jazz as the first important jazz composer. Deeper content (African-American history, spiritual issues), use of new forms (suites, rhapsodies, concertos), abandonment of the three-minute recording standard, new colorful arrangements, introduction of baritone saxophone. big band is Ellington's innovation, an autodidact who discovered it intuitively. The maestro drew his ideas from the rich and unique world of African-American folklore. Ellington's piano style was equally original. It was as if he put wide lines on the canvas (By the way, researchers of Ellington's work make such a parallel, because the musician loved to draw and paint pictures). His piano is Harlem's stride in "primal" energy, or descending paths flowing across the keyboard, or catchy chords.

The exact opposite of Ellington's "black" pianism is the style of C. Basie (1904-1984), who was apparently the first pianist of the laconic style. This musician performed very little and rarely. His piano part contrasts with the "luxurious" dense tutti of the big band. As a "response" to the orchestra's motor riffs and energetic

swing, Basie plays several notes, sometimes an interval or a chord or a small phrase. The maestro himself urged his colleagues to always listen not to notes, but to pauses, to use the musical space sparingly.

Pianists who appeared on the jazz scene in the 1940s, according to D. L. Collier in his book "The Formation of Jazz", are conditionally divided into two groups:

- 1) creators of the modern piano jazz style (A. Tatum, T. Monk, B. Powell);
- 2) representatives of the so-called "light piano style" (J. Shearing, O. Peterson, E. Garner).

A. Tatum (1909-1956), who was called the "eighth wonder of the world" during his lifetime due to his charming technique and ability to play at speeds of 370 and 420 beats per minute, can be partially considered his successor. Traditions founded by E. Hines. Blues and step piano elements, rapid flows from one hand to another - all this "points" us to Hines. But Tatum also has his own quirks. Thus, the musician, who is an excellent harmonizer, was able to change chords for almost every beat, enriching the harmonic scheme and not losing the swing (!) Tatum's style is so self-sufficient that he was assigned a rhythm section it was not necessary: the maestro himself repeated all the functions - bass line, accompaniment, all kinds of fillings. Not surprisingly, Muse-kant preferred a more solo format. Arguably, Tatum had the strongest influence on musicians, including bebop-era alto sax genius Charlie Parker, who was influenced by no other. In his "Encyclopedia of Jazz", L. Fehr notes that in a survey of a hundred pianists, seventy of them indicated A. Tatum as their main favorite.

All of the above pianists created the main tradition of piano jazz. On this instrument, performers skillfully used all styles (blues, boogie-woogie, piano, swing, bebop), techniques (locked hands), tricks (shifting from black keys to white). They were masters of spontaneous playing, developed and perfected the language of piano improvisation.

However, in the 1950s, new trends emerged in piano jazz related to cool jazz. This style, on the one hand, incorporated the best achievements of swing and bebop, and on the other hand, used the vocabulary of academic music. Musical instruments (flute, oboe, English horn, horn, tuba, mellophone) that were not used before in jazz performance appeared. Musicians studied the scores of Stravinsky, Ravel, Bartok, Hindemith, Honegger; as a result of the development of modern academic music, the melodic and harmonic language of jazz, as well as the arrangement, became more complex. Due to the dominance of brass, the sound became cool (hence the name "cool").

Pianists of the 1960s worked in accordance with all of the above styles and trends. Most of them performed strong hard bop (which was built on the achievements of bebop) and funk using the modal principle of improvisation, and skillfully repeated the characteristics of African-American vocals on the piano - "answers", ecstatic shouts, exclamations (K. Barron , M. Tyner, S. Clark, M. Longo, L. Ramsey, D. Mans, D. Pearson, B. Timmons, H. Silver, H. Tapscott, S. Walton, B. Harris, et al.). S. Taylor, Sun Ra, D. Burrell, L. Tristano, P. Blay, S. Rivers and other performers dedicated to the anarchic ideas of free jazz. Some pianists have sought to change piano technique and texture, introduce new techniques, and expand their understanding of the instrument. Thus, Cecil Taylor (1929-2018) used the atonal-percussion method: he looked at the piano as a set of drums, often using cluster chords. By the way, V. Sargent in his book "Jazz: Genesis, Musical Language, Aesthetics" emphasizes the rhythmic-percussive function of the piano and "uses" us, in turn, to Stravinsky. McCoy Tyner (1938-2020), legendary member of the John Coltrane Quartet, introduced fourth chords to jazz pianists.

References:

1. Bulatnov S. Earl Hines [Elektron resurs]. URL: <http://bulswing.ru/?p=781> (kirish sanasi: 17.02.2020).
2. Jazzning buyuk odamlari / tahr. K. Moshkova. Sankt-Peterburg: Doe; PLANET MUSIQA, 2009. 736 b.
3. Vermenich Yu. Jazz: tarix, uslublar, ustalar. 2-nashr, ster. Sankt-Peterburg: Doe; PLANET MUSIQA, 2009. 607 b.
4. Vermenich Yu. ...Va bu jazz. Sankt-Peterburg: Nevskiy jamg'armasi, 2005. 448 p.
5. Collier J. L. Jazzning shakllanishi. M.: Raduga, 1984. 411 b.
6. Kornev P.K.XX asrning 30-40-yillaridagi jazz pianino ijrosi.Rossiya davlat pedagogika universitetining "Izvestiya". A. I. Gertsen. 2008. No 58. S. 149-158.
7. Korolev O. K. Jazz, rok va pop musiqasining qisqacha ensiklopedik lug'ati. Atamalar va tushunchalar. M.: Muzika, 2006. 168 b.
8. Kurakin I. Herbi Xankok jazzni globallashtiradi // Madaniyat. 2009 yil. 32-son.
9. Kharatova Shakhlo "USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS" Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;

